

The Influence of Emergency Department Information System (EDIS) in the Quality of Health Data: The Case of Muhimbili National Hospital

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Suggested Citation

Mashoka, R.J., Lwoga, E.T., Komba, M.M., Mfinanga, J., Kilindimo, S., & Sawe, H. (2024). The Influence of Emergency Department Information System (EDIS) in the Quality of Health Data: The Case of Muhimbili National Hospital. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(4), 574-584.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(4\).49](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(4).49)

Abstract:

The study investigated the extent to which the EDIS is adopted among health care workers at the Muhimbili National Hospital – Emergency Medicine Department (MNH – ED), EDIS data quality among health care workers at MNH – ED and the influence of using EDIS to health data quality improvement at MNH. The study used mixed research approach where both quantitative and qualitative techniques were utilized. Data collected by using questionnaire and Interview. Total of 220 out of 238 respondents completed the survey and 6 employees from the Emergency Department (ED) were interviewed. Respondents of this study obtained from ED at MNH. It is further reported that accuracy of data has significant positive impact on Effective use of EDIS ($\beta = 0.282$, $P = 0.024$). Results

indicated that, completeness of data have significant positive impact on Effective use of EDIS ($\beta = 0.426$, $P = 0.046$). Moreover, the results indicated that, consistency of data have significant positive impact on Effective use of EDIS ($\beta = 0.249$, $P = 0.034$). Results indicated that, timeliness of data have significant positive impact on Effective use of EDIS ($\beta = 0.518$, $P = 0.000$). Moreover, effective use of EDIS has a positive effect on improved data quality outcomes. This implies that use of EDIS indicators including ease of use had ($\beta = 0.123$, $p\text{-value} = 0.014$), Suitability for the task had ($\beta = 0.360$, $p = 0.003$) and user satisfaction had ($\beta = 0.32$, $p = 0.004$) which have significant positive impact on outcome of data quality.

Keywords: *Emergency Department Information System (EDIS), Information System Success Model (ISS), Emergency Department (ED).*

Introduction

EDIS has been designed specifically to manage data and workflow in support of ED patient care and operations (Clark, 2017). EDIS as an Information System (IS) that can be implemented either as a subsystem of the hospital information system or a standalone system in the ED (Saghaeiannjad-Isfahani et al., 2019). The implementation of EDIS is expected to improve the overall quality of health data in the ED.

Some of the countries that have adopted EDIS in sub-Saharan Africa include South Africa, Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda, Ghana, Mozambique, Rwanda, Nigeria, Malawi, Guinea Bissau, Cameroon, Congo, Angola, Botswana and Mali (Kumwenda et al., 2014).

In Tanzania, EDIS was installed in 2015 at the Muhimbili National Hospital (MNH) and it was deployed only at ED. The system aimed to improve the quality of health data by reducing patient wait times, managing emergency patient data and generally improving patient care at the minimum costs across the department.

Hence, this study is expected to complement existing literature on the use of EDIS and its implications for quality health care in the country. Therefore, study examined the use of EDIS in improving the quality of health data at MNH-ED.

Materials and Methods

In examining EDIS adoption in the United States, Landman et al (2010) found that the widespread adoption of EDIS is required so as to realize the potential gains in efficiency, cost savings and improved quality resulted from EDIS. The study found that EDIS is not greatly widespread in US with exception of urban areas and the areas specializing in paediatric services. The study concluded that there is a need to formulate specific incentive mechanisms for adoption and implementation of EDIS. EDIS's usability analysis as presented by Shapiro et al (2010) explored much on the challenges in

employing the EDIS while concurrently providing quality patient care and reducing risk. The study revealed that, there is still an adoption gap among the users of the system that is expert and novice nurses. While the later were dissatisfied with the system and blamed it for limited rates of efficiency in supporting tasks, the former opined otherwise.

The study revealed that in EMS, data completeness, data accuracy, consistency and timeliness are very important for improving quality of care and for making right decisions and promote quality of information flow across the healthcare organisation. The study conducted by Ahanhanzo et al. (2014) revealed that most of the developing countries are challenged with the issue of poor quality of health data that limits the usefulness of their health systems including the EDIS. However, it is recorded in the study conducted by Riain and Helfert (2005) data quality issues are not only a problem in developing countries, they are also common in the Southern European countries such as Italy and Portugal.

Moreover, loss in revenue and increased number of deaths in hospitals each year may be realized (Riain & Helfert, 2005), affect the ED patient flow and increased inefficiencies in overall ED operations (Grafstein et al., 2008). Other outcomes include communication failure, wrong order, wrong patient errors, poor data display and alert fatigue (Farley et al., 2013). These outcomes do differ from place to place depending on other factors that are associated with various challenges in specific areas. Thus, the researcher wanted to obtain specific data on such outcomes in the Tanzanian contexts and most especially at MNH-ED.

Information System Success Model (ISS)

In this study, the measure of the data quality was more elaborated through Data Quality Review Tool (DQR). Data Quality Review (DQR) is a framework and methodology that builds on the earlier program specific data quality tools and methods by providing standardized metrics for measurement of data quality, proposing a

harmonized approach to measuring and improving data quality and including tools that can be adopted by users.

The DQR is expected to contribute to improvement of quality of data used by countries in reviewing the progress and performance of projects and hence facilitating decision making. DQR is aimed at institutionalizing a system for assessing quality of data including routine monitoring of data, independent annual data quality reviews and periodic in-depth assessments of priority health programmes identifying the weakness in the data management system and monitoring the performance of data quality over time.

The tool underlined various data quality metrics, which are a set of standard indicators that are routinely reported through facility information systems and quantifies problems of data completeness, timeliness, consistency and accuracy in order to ensure that health facility data are fit for purpose.

Data quality review (DQR) proposed by WHO stipulated data quality dimensions that can be adopted in assessing the data quality in various health systems. Such dimensions are completeness, accuracy, consistency and timeliness. Various studies by different scholars (Gao & Koronios, 2012; Murphy et al., 2014; Koronios et al., 2010; Chen et al, 2014; Ward et al, 2013), have used these four dimensions to assess data quality in the ED.

In most cases, data completeness and data accuracy were found to be the most important dimensions in improving the quality of care and for making right decisions. Data consistency is very important in showing the agreement between two or more sources of information and the linkage between primary and secondary care systems. It promotes the quality of communication and information flow across the healthcare organisations.

Accuracy of data measures the extent to which data is correct and reliable. The accuracy of data is very important and it is supposed to be traced from the entry level. Data should be entered into the system with a high rate of accuracy so as to

be used in supporting decision (Dawson et al., 2015). Any inaccuracies and incompleteness should be addressed immediately so as to make sure the data that are in the health care are more accurate (Hunt et al., 2007).

Completeness of data measures the extent to which data is not missing and is of sufficient breadth and depth for the task at hand. Various studies conducted in health care services suggested that data maintained in the system should be complete to be useful in making decisions (Dawson et al., 2015; Hunt et al., 2007; Porter et al., 2010).

Consistency of data measures the extent to which the representation of data values remains the same in multiple data items in multiple locations. Data consistency is very important in showing the agreement between various sources of information and in linking between the primary and secondary care systems. This assists in promoting the quality of communication and information flow across healthcare organisations (Mashoufi et al., 2018).

Timeliness measure the extent to which the data are sufficiently up to date for the task at hand. Various studies conducted on the health care services agreed that for the characteristics of emergency medical services the data/information should be accessible so as to treat patients in the timely manner (Ward et al., 2013; Ward et al., 2015).

Effective EDIS use is measured through its ease of use, usefulness, ease of learning, user satisfaction and suitability for the task (Farzandipour et al, 2019). EDIS was found to be an effective application for managing workflows in the emergency department. Different health institutions use the Emergency Department Information System (EDIS) to assist them in the management of emergency departments (Bennett & Hardiker, 2017).

This system is both a workflow and a data collection tool designed to capture real-time information about patients, and to support the operational control of Health emergency departments.

Methodology

The study employed the mixed research design that allowed researchers to use both quantitative and qualitative approaches in collecting and analysing data (Schoonenboom & Johnson, 2017). The quantitative approach was used in assessing the extent to which the EDIS is adopted among the health care workers, the EDIS data quality among care workers which were done by assessing five quality dimensions which are accuracy, completeness, reliability, relevance and timelines. Moreover, it was applied in examining the outcomes of EDIS data quality at MNH. Generally, all the research objectives were addressed through the use of quantitative approach.

The study was carried out at the Muhimbili National Hospital (MNH) in Dar es Salaam and precisely at the Upanga branch. MNH was used as a case study area because it is the leading hospital in Tanzania and it is referred as a National Hospital in Tanzania. In general, because MNH employs 2700 health care personnel, they form the population of this study. Such number of employees work under 8 directorates that are Medical services, Surgical Services, Nursing & Quality Services, Clinical Support Services, Human Resources, Finance and Planning, Technical Services, and Information & Communications Technology (WHO, 2010). The total number of employees working under EMD is 238 and the survey contacted all the employees of this department.

In this study, the researcher used questionnaires that were distributed to the EMD staff who are functionally the primary user of the EDIS at MNH. The questions comprised both close-ended and open-ended questions. A researcher included Likert scale questions to capture attitudes and perceptions of respondents. The research questions were connected to EDIS adoption among healthcare workers, EDIS data quality and outcomes of EDIS data quality at MNH. Also, interview was used in this study as the complimentary to questionnaire. A set of pre-set questions were administered to a selected set of staff based on their knowledge and experience in using EDIS.

Table 1. Composition of MNH Employees under EMD

Sn	Staff	Number of Staff
1	EM Registrars	14
2	EM Residents	46
3	EM Specialists	16
4	EM Nurses	78
5	EM Health Attendants	56
6	EM Cashiers	7
7	EM Social Works	8
8	EM Medical Records	8
9	EM ICT Person	3
10	EM Drivers	2
Total Number of Staff in EMD		238

The interviewed staff were purposively obtained. The researcher ensured that interviews were held to information rich and experienced staff in using EDIS In that regard, the ICT experts and head of MNH –ED were considered.

Results

EDIS adoption among health care workers

In addressing the research objective concerning EDIS adoption among the health care workers, various questions were asked to achieve this objective as seen in the Table 2.

Assessment of EDIS Data Quality among Health Care Workers

In addressing the research objective concerning the assessment of EDIS data quality among healthcare workers, the respondents were presented with 3 Likert scale statements ranging from 1 as disagree to 3 agree. The respondents were required to rate various statements on data quality dimensions based on their experience of using EDIS as shown in Table 3.

Assessment of the Outcomes of EDIS data quality at MNH

The respondents were required to rate various statements on the outcomes of EDIS based on their experience of using EDIS as shown in Table 4.

Table 2. EDIS Adoption among Health Care Workers

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Use of other Hospital Information System		
Yes	211	96%
No	9	4%
Number of years spent on other Hospital Information System		
5 years - 10 years	155	70%
1 year - 5 years	47	21%
Above 10 years	18	8%
EDIS Users		
Yes	209	95%
No	11	5%
Extent on using EDIS		
Yes	209	95%
No	11	5%
EDIS centralization of Emergency Medical Department (EDM) patients' services		
No	186	85%
Yes	34	15%
EDIS reduced queue to patients		
Yes	154	70%
No	66	30%
EDIS improved access to data		
No	154	70%
Yes	66	30%
EDIS improved the services offered in MNH - ED		
Yes	152	69%
No	68	31%

Table 3. Assessment of EDIS Data Quality among Health Care Workers

Characteristics	Disagree	%	Neutral	%	Agree	%
Completeness data dimension						
The data in EDIS has sufficient breadth and depth for our work.	54	25%	21	10%	145	66%
The data in EDIS are sufficient complete for our needs	58	26%	32	15%	130	59%
Data in the EDIS are complete	42	19%	90	41%	88	40%
The data in EDIS includes all the necessary values	54	25%	82	37%	84	38%
Timeliness data dimension						
Data in EDIS arrive on time	42	19%	12	5%	166	75%
In EDIS, the time interval from data collection and processing to release meets requirements	60	28%	15	7%	136	64%
Data in EDIS are regularly updated	42	19%	52	24%	126	57%
Consistency data dimension						
After data have been processed in the EDIS, their concepts, value domains, and formats still match as before processing	36	16%	18	8%	166	75%
During a certain time, data remain consistent and verifiable in the EDIS	77	35%	16	7%	127	58%
Data from the other sources are consistent verifiable in EDIS	56	25%	58	26%	106	48%
Accuracy data dimension						

Data presentation in EDIS well reflects the true state of the source information	76	35%	13	6%	131	60%
Data representation in EDIS will not cause ambiguity.	103	47%	11	5%	106	48%
Data provided by EDIS are accurate	62	28%	88	40%	70	32%

Note: Four data quality dimensions were examined in this study, including completeness, timeliness, consistency and accuracy.

Table 4. Assessment of the Outcome of EDIS Data Quality at MNH

Characteristics	Disagree	%	Neutral	%	Agree	%
Outcomes of EDIS at MNH						
Overdependence on the EDIS increased the risks to ED operations when the EDIS is not operating	19	9%	15	7%	186	85%
EDIS accelerated poor documentation	80	36%	9	4%	131	60%
EDIS is associated with communication failure	85	39%	19	9%	116	53%
EDIS affected the patient flow in overall ED operations	83	38%	26	12%	111	50%
EDIS has increased patient waiting times and crowding	122	55%	11	5%	87	40%
EDIS affected the patient flow in overall ED operations	83	38%	26	12%	111	50%
EDIS has increased patient waiting times and crowding	122	55%	11	5%	87	40%
Poor data display in EDIS	109	50%	23	10%	88	40%
Most of the data in EDIS are incomplete	116	53%	21	10%	83	38%
EDIS has led to medical errors and cause patient safety and quality concerns	110	50%	29	13%	81	37%
EDIS is associated with wrong order – wrong patient errors	109	50%	31	14%	80	36%
EDIS has attributed for inefficiencies in ED operations due data inconsistencies	122	55%	42	19%	56	25%
EDIS has increased the cost of providing patient care across the department	170	77%	15	7%	35	16%

Note: The study contacted key informants to explore more on the outcomes of EDIS data quality following the implementation of the said system.

Discussion

Assess the Extent to which the EDIS is Adopted among Health Care Workers at MNH-ED

Generally, the findings revealed that EDIS has been adopted in running ED operations at MNH, with the data revealing that the majority of respondents (95%) were using EDIS in their operations. This implied that the system has accommodated numerous operations in the ED, making it necessary for users to use the system in providing healthcare to patients.

Furthermore, the findings revealed that the majority of respondents (88%) used EDIS at MNH on a daily basis. Further analysis on the adoption of EDIS in MNH revealed that, the majority of respondents (92%) used EDIS for

more than 2 hours per day, with only 8% using EDIS for less than one hour per day.

The adoption of EDIS system can further be analysed in terms of user perception regarding the system use. Findings revealed that despite of the large number of users who are using EDIS at MNH, a significant proportion of respondents argued that EDIS has not yet improved the services offered at MNH - ED. Furthermore, findings reveal that the adoption of EDIS has not improved access to data and also EDIS has not reduced queues to patients. This finding revealed that although the extent to which EDIS has been adopted at MNH has been assessed, but the perspectives of the users regarding the use and the adoption of EDIS do differ. This evidence congruent with the findings from Vezyridis et al.,(2012) who argued that different

users of the EDIS have different attitudes and experiences with the system. While some users believe that the system is supportive in their daily practise, others consider it disruptive in their daily practise. Moreover, a study by Shapiro et al. (2010) has earlier established the adoption gap among different system users. The study conducted by Mayer et al (2010), on the other hand, stated that learning curve effects will be observed among users of the new system.

Therefore, based on findings study conclude that, the wide spread adoption of EDIS is important in organization in order to capture those potential gains since EDIS can be used so as to achieve the desired results on health care services provision. The EDIS can be extended to various departments in healthcare organisations.

To Assess the Data Quality of EDIS among Health Care Workers at MNH-ED

The study had a bunch of findings on this objective. Based on descriptive analysis, the findings on the data quality dimensions found that, 51% of respondents argued that the data in EDIS are complete, they include all the necessary values, are sufficiently complete for the particular needs and they also had sufficient breadth and depth for the particular work. Regarding the timeliness as one of the data quality dimensions, the findings revealed that the average of 66% of the respondents agree that data in EDIS arrive on time, are regularly updated and that the time interval from data collection and processing to release meets requirements.

With regard to consistency, it was revealed that the average of 60% of the respondents in this study agreed that after data have been processed in EDIS, their concepts, value domains, and formats still match as before processing, data in the EDIS remain consistent and verifiable and data in EDIS and the data from the other sources are consistent verifiable in EDIS. The findings on the accuracy of data in the EDIS revealed that an average of 47% of respondents agreed on several statements that show that the data in EDIS is accurate. However, a reasonable per cent of respondents disagreed meaning that

there as issues regarding accuracy of data in EDIS. Leaving out 37% of respondents who disagree. General findings on the EDIS data quality assessments revealed that the EDIS data are timely processed, consistent, complete and accuracy. By ranking the data quality dimensions, it shows that the data quality dimensions of timeliness and consistency were more evident in EDIS than completeness and accuracy.

Based on regression analysis, the results indicated that, accuracy of data have significant positive impact on Effective use of EDIS ($\beta = 0.282, P = 0.024$). Also, the results indicated that, completeness of data have significant positive impact on Effective use of EDIS ($\beta = 0.426, P = 0.046$). Moreover, the results indicated that, consistency of data have significant positive impact on Effective use of EDIS ($\beta = 0.249, P = 0.034$). The results indicated that, timeliness of data have significant positive impact on Effective use of EDIS ($\beta = 0.518, P = 0.000$). Such values imply that, all data quality dimensions have impacts on EDIS data quality.

Generally, the findings demonstrated that the data in EDIS are processed, retrieved on time, with consistence and completeness. The findings provide the evidence that EDIS is very useful in running various operations in the ED at MNH. The findings from this study congruent with findings that were documented in other empirical studies. For instance a study by Ahanhanzo et al., (2014) found that the quality of data in any health system is the key to the usefulness of the particular system in supporting decision making. In line to these findings, a study by Mashouti, et al. (2018) reports that basically the data completeness, data accuracy, consistency and timeliness are very important for improving quality of care and for making right decisions and promoting quality of information flow across the healthcare organisation.

Therefore, based on findings it can be concluded that data quality of DIS is an important issue due to high turnover and speed of work issues experiences in this department which increases the possibility of making errors.

Improved Data Quality of EDIS at MNH

The implementation of EDIS at MNH has had an influence on ED operations as well as the overall provision of health care to patients. Due to data consistency and completeness, EDIS has contributed to efficiency in ED operations, reduced wrong order - wrong patient errors, reduced patient waiting times and crowding, and reduced the cost of providing patient care across the department.

On the other hand, there are evidences of negative outcomes experienced by the users of EDIS at MNH, including medical errors and also the patient flow in the overall ED operations has been affected by EDIS. Moreover, the use of EDIS has accelerated poor documentation and communication failure. In addition, overdependence on EDIS increases the risks to ED operations when the EDIS is not operating.

Moreover, the regression results shown that, effective usage of EDIS is statistically significant to the outcome of data quality. Through measurement of EDIS use, the results indicated that ease of use and learning has a significant positive impact on outcome of data quality with estimated coefficient (β) of 0.123 sig (p-value) of 0.014. Suitability for the task has a significant positive impact on outcome of data quality with estimated coefficient (β) of 0.360 and sig (p-value) of 0.003.

The findings obtained in this study are in congruence with those obtained in previous studies conducted on the benefits of implementing EDIS in various areas. For instance, a study conducted by Bennett & Hardiker (2017) pointed out that implementation of EDIS improves efficiency in providing patient care and enhances the provision of health services to the patients at minimum costs. The findings show that EDIS has reduced inconsistencies and patient waiting times and crowding at MNH. Findings are also in line with those provided by Saghaeiannejad-Isfahani et al. (2019) who noted that, the implementation of EDIS has been very useful in managing patient flow, patient waiting times and crowding.

Moreover, considering the negative impacts resulting from implementing EDIS at MNH, they echo those previously mentioned by different scholars. Studies by Mogashoa (2014) and Farley et al (2013) present that the implementation of EDIS in most developing countries especially in SSA are characterized by poor quality health data which lead to medical errors, communication failure, wrong order – wrong patient errors and other related issues. Basically, the series of various negative outcomes from the implementation of EDIS are associated with the poor quality of the health data in EDIS.

Conclusion

This study obtained various findings regarding the specific objectives of this study. The use of EDIS in improving health quality at MNH was the core issue in undertaking this study. This study concluded that, the introduction and adoption of EDIS in Tanzania especially at MNH has been one of the remarkable developments as far as the hospital systems are concerned. The success of any system depends on the user acceptance and the user's involvement in various stages of implementing the system. This has been the case for the EDIS whereby the majority of the respondents have adopted the use of EDIS in conducting their daily operations.

The identified challenges regarding the use and the implementation of EDIS has been associated with lack of regular trainings on the usage of the system and limited continual knowledge sharing among the staff who are using the particular system. On the other hand, the success of implementing EDIS at MNH depends on the quality of data in system. EDIS data quality assessment results are the input of data quality that are maintained in the system.

The knowledge on the effective usage of the system and the compliance of the users in using the system according to the guidance enhance the improvements of EDIS data quality. Once all the data dimension attributes are fulfilled, then the quality of data will be improved and hence EDIS will be successful in running EMD

operations at MNH. In this case, each stakeholder of the EDIS, should make sure that data filled in the system are complete and are of high quality so as to get the final results that might help in making various managerial decisions. The chances of attaining the intended objectives of introducing and implementation EDIS at MNH are very high and through the continual system audit and implementation of the recommended measures, the system will usefully make more improvements in EMD operations.

Few challenges identified including poor documentation and communication failure caused by the use of EDIS can easily be controlled through implementing enough trainings on system usage and the use of expatriate recommendations concerning EDIS.

Acknowledgement

I would like to thank Almighty God for all that He has done over the course of my career. His Grace has given me various reasons to successfully complete of this research study.

I extend my sincere gratitude to all authors of this study for their tireless efforts and guidance in conducting this study. With their daily encouragement and guidance, we have succeeded in achieving this goal.

Finally, I would like to extend my heartfelt appreciations to Muhimbili National Hospital (MNH) staff, especially those working in EMD, for their relentless and dedicated support, time and efforts they accorded me with. Though their positive cooperation, I obtained necessary inputs that facilitated me to accomplish this endeavour.

Conflict of Interest

No Conflict of interest

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